

Holospora-like bacteria “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*” and *Preeria caryophila*: Ultrastructure, promiscuity, and biogeography of the symbionts

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Abstract

Two already known representatives of *Holospora*-like bacteria, “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*” from *Paramecium putrinum* and *Preeria caryophila*, originally retrieved from the *Paramecium aurelia* complex, were found in new hosts: *Paramecium nephridiatum* and *Paramecium polycaryum*, respectively. In the present study, these bacteria were investigated using morphological and molecular methods. For “*Ca. G. yakutica*”, the first details of the electron microscopic structure in the main and new hosts were provided. Regarding *Pr. caryophila*, the ultrastructural description of this species was implemented by several features previously unknown, such as the so called “membrane cluster” dividing periplasm from cytoplasm and fine composition of infectious forms before and during its releasing from the infected macronucleus. The new combinations of these *Holospora*-like bacteria with ciliate hosts were discussed from biogeographical and ecological points of view. Host specificity of symbionts as a general paradigm was critically reviewed as well.

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Introduction

Paramecium (Ciliophora, Oligohymenophorea) is one of the most studied ciliate genera, which comprises now about 20 valid morphospecies (Fokin, 2010/2011; Krenek et al., 2015; Przyboś and Tarcz, 2018; Potekhin and Mayén-

Estrada, 2020; Serra et al., 2020, Melekhin et al., 2022). *Holospora* and similar infectious intranuclear bacteria, found either in the macronucleus (Ma) or in the micronucleus (Mi) known generally as *Holospora*-like bacteria (HLB), belong to the family *Holosporaceae* (*Pseudomonadota*, *Alphaproteobacteria*). To date, these bacteria or their relatives were found in representatives of five classes of

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Ciliophora: Oligohymenophorea, Heterotrichea, Armophorea, Phyllopharyngea, and Prostomatea (Görtz, 1986; Fokin, 2004, 2012; Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Serra et al., 2016; Fokin et al., 2019; Schrallhammer and Potekhin, 2020; Potekhin et al., 2021; Fokin and Serra, 2022), even if there are no molecular characterization of HLB outside *Peniculia* yet. However, oligohymenophorean ciliates, namely members of the genus *Paramecium*, should be treated as the main hosts of such intranuclear bacteria (Fokin, 1989, Fokin and Sabaneeya 1993; Fokin et al., 1996, 1999; Fokin, 2000; Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Boscaro et al., 2013; Serra et al., 2016; Schrallhammer and Potekhin, 2020). Basically, for many of HLB the strict host specificity was considered as one of their most distinctive traits. The suitable host allows them to complete their life cycle, and the association may stay alive and stable in the laboratory conditions sometimes for dozens of years. However, several HLB were detected in different (even usually close related) host species either during experiments or in some natural populations (Fujishima and Fujita, 1985; Görtz, 1986, 1987; Fokin, 1993, 2000, 2004).

In this work, we use De Bary's definition of "symbiosis" as "the living together of two differently named organisms" (de Bary, 1879), independent of effects on the organisms involved, thereby including mutualism, commensalism, and parasitism. The terms "symbionts" and "endosymbionts" also follow this definition.

Unfortunately, for many HLB we do not possess a complete set of data, and for many of them the molecular characterization is still lacking. Indeed, many symbionts were not deeply investigated as the infection, in many cases, was found during morphological studies of the ciliate host or these studies were performed much before "the molecular era".

Nonetheless, the research in this field is ongoing, and when some lucky findings of such HLB endosymbionts happen, it becomes possible to fill the gaps in the existing data and to learn more. It is the case of two recent findings concerning "*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*" and *Preeria caryophila* found in new hosts: *Paramecium nephridiatum* and *Paramecium polycaryum*, respectively.

"*Ca. G. yakutica*" was firstly described as the macronuclear symbiont of *P. putrinum*, and named after the area where it had been found, Yakutia (Russia) (Beliavskaia et al., 2020). However, quite probably the same or at least very similar HLB was previously detected in *P. putrinum* strain retrieved from Karlsruhe, Germany (Fokin et al., 1996, 1999). The other HLB in focus, previously known as *Holospora caryophila*, was redescribed few years ago as a new genus representative, *Pr. caryophila* (Potekhin et al., 2018). It is known as the macronuclear symbiont of some species of the *P. aurelia* complex and *P. caudatum*.

In the present work we describe two new combinations of these HLB with the different hosts: "*Ca. G. yakutica*" that we found in the Ma of *P. nephridiatum* isolated from the Baltic Sea coastline, and *Pr. caryophila* retrieved in the Ma of *P.*

polycaryum collected from Egypt. Since in the above-mentioned articles, the ultrastructural morphology of the symbiont described from the Yakutia population of *P. putrinum* was not presented (Beliavskaia et al., 2020) and for *Pr. caryophila* some ultrastructural details were missing (Potekhin et al., 2018), with the present study we are trying to fill these gaps. Starting from these interesting new datasets we take the chance to treat the paradigm of host specificity of symbionts in ciliates and discuss it in frames of the past and recent literature data. Moreover, the new combinations of HLB-*Paramecium* spp. are discussed also from a biogeographical and an ecological point of view.

Material and methods

Host isolation, cultivation, and identification

The species identification of the infected *Paramecium* cells was assessed by means of morphological features (Fokin, 2010/2011) and further confirmed by molecular data.

Infection of the Ma with some kind of HLB was found in *P. nephridiatum* cells isolated from the mixed population, where *P. caudatum* and *P. woodruffi* were also detected. The sample was taken by N. Lebedeva in the coastal vegetation of the Haapsalu Bay (Estonia, N 58° 95' 18", E 23° 52' 44") with water salinity 6‰, in the beginning of June 2019. The infection prevalence within *P. nephridiatum* population was about 25%. Subcloning did not yield a result: all clones died. Thus, for further investigations the native population EHa3 of the infected *P. nephridiatum* was used. For the laboratory maintenance of the EHa3 culture, the lettuce medium inoculated with *Enterobacter aerogenes* supplied with beta-sitosterol (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany, 0.2 mg/l) was used. The population was kept under salinity 5‰ at 18° C.

Cells of *P. polycaryum* with infected Ma were detected in the sample collected by A. Rychkova in a small artificial water canal of the Alameen Desert, Egypt (N 30° 55' 19", E 28° 43' 08") in the beginning of December 2019. It was a part of the mixed *Paramecium* population including some cells of *P. aurelia* and *P. bursaria* too. Many *P. polycaryum* cells contained several different bacterial symbionts in cytoplasm and Ma (N. Lebedeva, unpublished). After subcloning the infected line EgA-21 was obtained. In all cells of this clone only one intranuclear symbiont morphologically resembling *Pr. caryophila* was detected. The culture was kept on lettuce medium inoculated with *E. aerogenes* with adding of beta-sitosterol (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany, 0.2 mg/l) at 21° C.

Main *Paramecium* cultures used in this study are maintained in RC CCM collection (World Data Centre for Microorganisms, RN 1171) of St. Petersburg State University, Russia.

General morphology and ultrastructure of the new isolates of HLB from the Ma of *P. nephridiatum* and *P. polycaryum* were compared with the light microscopical and transmission electron microscopical (TEM) images of HLB previously taken for *P. putrinum* strain PpKH1-1 (quite probably “*Ca. G. yakutica*”), collected in Karlsruhe, Germany, in June 1995 and for the symbionts which were determined as *Pr. caryophila* in *P. biaurelia* strain PnMS212, collected in Münster, Germany and *H. undulata* in *P. caudatum* strain PcSK12, collected in Stuttgart, Germany (Fokin et al., 1996).

Light and transmission electron microscopy

Living cells of the investigated ciliate strains were observed for morphological details with the Leitz and Zeiss Axioskop (Germany) and with the Nikon Eclipse Ni microscope equipped with a DS-Fi3 camera (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan), both with differential interference contrast (DIC) at a magnification \times 300–1250. A compression device (Skovorodkin, 1990) and a mechanical microcompressor Commodore (Yan et al., 2014) were used to immobilize and observe the cells. Specimens with HLB were fixed for electron microscopy according to Fokin and Görtz (1993) and examined with the SX 100S JEOL, Tokyo, Japan transmission electron microscope.

DNA extraction and molecular characterization

Paramecium nephridiatum and “*Ca. G. yakutica*”: three cells of *P. nephridiatum* were carefully washed with distilled water, then transferred in PBS and processed accordingly to the manufacturer instruction of REPLI-g Single Cell Kit (QIAGEN, Hilden, Germany) to perform the whole genome amplification. The product of the reaction was then used to perform a 18S rDNA and a 16S rDNA targeting polymerase chain reaction (PCR), for the host and the symbiont, respectively. Amplification and sequencing of the two genes were carried out using universal primers, according to Serra et al. (2016). The same procedure was applied to the other association under study, *P. polycaryum* and *Pr. caryophila*, with the difference that five selected cells with symbionts were washed overnight in Volvic water, and then transferred not into PBS but to sterile water for further whole genome amplification.

Fluorescence *in situ* hybridization (FISH) analyses

The eubacterial universal probe EUB338 (Amann et al., 1990) was employed in FISH experiments to highlight the presence of bacteria inside the ciliate cells. The probe Alf1b for *Alphaproteobacteria* (Manz et al., 1992) was used as well. FISH was performed as described in Fokin et al. (1996) and Serra et al. (2016).

Experimental infections

Experimental bacterial infection with HLB from *P. polycaryum* was carried out using a homogenate prepared from infected cells according to Preer (1969). In particular, aposymbiotic cells ($n = 20$ – 25) were infected by mixing equal volumes of the medium with a cell set and the homogenate in a depression slide, and maintained at 21° C. To check the infection development, at least 5–10 living cells were observed one, two and four weeks after experimental infection.

For these experiments 14 aposymbiotic strains of *P. polycaryum* collected from different places of Europe and India as well as 10 strains of the *P. aurelia* species complex - *P. biaurelia*, *P. triaurelia*, *P. pentaurelia*, *P. sexaurelia*, *P. octaurelia*, and *P. novaurelia* and two strains of *P. caudatum* were used as recipients. The infection with homogenate was performed for each recipient strain twice. Then experimental infection by co-cultivation procedure was attempted three times for the strains of the *P. aurelia* complex and *P. caudatum*. Given that transinfection experiments, on average, have an extremely low success rate and that our intention was to evaluate if a *Preeria* isolated from a specific host was able to infect and develop into different host species, we selected as possible recipients only a sub-set of paramecia i.e. species in which *Preeria* had been previously recorded. Therefore we selected strains of *P. caudatum*, and the above mentioned *P. aurelia* species as possible recipients.

Experimental infection with HLB from *P. nephridiatum* was performed in two different ways: by co-cultivation of one hyperinfected cell with aposymbiotic cells or by mixing a droplet of medium where a single hyperinfected cell of EHa3 strain was crashed, with several aposymbiotic cells. The homogenate infection procedure was not used as there were not enough infected paramecia to prepare homogenate. Seven strains of *P. nephridiatum* and two strains of *P. woodruffi*, which have been isolated from the same native population EHa3 were used as recipients in two repetitions.

Phylogenetic analyses

The 18S rDNA sequences of *P. nephridiatum* EHa3 and *P. polycaryum* EgA-21 were aligned with the automatic aligner of the ARB software package version 5.5 (Westram et al., 2011) on the SSU ref NR99 SILVA database (Quast et al., 2013), manually updated with latest released sequences.

For the phylogenetic analysis, other 41 18S rDNA sequences belonging to the representatives of the genus *Paramecium* were selected, for a total of 43 sequences. After manual editing to optimise base pairing in the predicted rRNA stem regions, the alignment was trimmed at both ends to the length of the shortest sequence. The result-

ing matrix contained 1,625 nucleotides, and was used for phylogenetic reconstructions.

The optimal substitution model was selected with jModelTest 2.1 (Darriba et al., 2011) according to the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The maximum likelihood (ML) tree was inferred with PHYML version 2.4 (Guindon and Gascuel, 2003) from the ARB package, performing 100 pseudo-replicates. Bayesian inference (BI) tree was inferred with MrBayes 3.2, using three runs, each with one cold and three heated Monte Carlo Markov chains, iterating for 1,000,000 generations with a burn-in of 25%.

For the phylogenetic analysis of HLB endosymbionts, their 16S rDNA sequences were aligned with the automatic aligner of the ARB software package to the SSU ref NR99 132 SILVA database, and the alignment was manually refined to optimise base pairing in the predicted rRNA structure. The final selection for the phylogeny included 55 sequences, 45 of which belonged to other representatives of family *Holosporaceae* as ingroup, and 8 members of the family *Caedimonadaceae* were used as an outgroup. The alignment of selected sequences was trimmed at both ends to the length of the shortest sequence and keeping all internal positions, resulting in 1,275 nucleotide columns. The best substitution model was selected with jModeltest according to the AIC. ML and BI inference phylogenies were then estimated respectively with PHYML, with 1,000 pseudo-replicates, and MrBayes, with three runs of three heated and one cold chain iterating for 1,000,000, and applying a burn-in of 25%.

Results

Identification of the hosts

The morphological investigation of the newly isolated *Paramecium* strains, HEa3 and EgA-21, revealed that they belong to *P. nephridiatum* and *P. polycaryum* (Fokin, 1997, 2010/11; Fokin and Chivilev, 1999, 2000), respectively. *Paramecium nephridiatum* HEa3 was characterized by a 130–160 μm cell length, 2–6 endosomal-type micronuclei and from 2 to 3 pores of contractile vacuoles. *Paramecium polycaryum* EgA-21 was characterized by a 75–110 μm cell length, 2–4 vesicular-type micronuclei and a single pore of contractile vacuoles.

The obtained 18S rDNA sequences of *P. nephridiatum* HEa3 and *P. polycaryum* EgA-21 (1,730 bp and 1,751 bp, accession numbers OQ548095 and OQ548096, respectively) and related phylogeny confirmed this identification as well (Supplementary Fig. 1). Indeed, from BLAST search on NCBI, the sequences of HEa3 and EgA-21 strains resulted 100% identical to *P. nephridiatum* strain BMS16-23 (MK764889) and 99.82% identical to *P. polycaryum* strain GD1 (LT628488), respectively. In the phylogenetic analysis these two sequences clustered with other

P. nephridiatum and *P. polycaryum* sequences with high statistical support (ML/BI: 92/1.00 and 100/1.00) in both cases (Supplementary Fig. 1). The ML and BI trees resulted substantially identical.

HLB of *Paramecium nephridiatum* HEa3 – “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*”

Bacterial infection of the Ma in the *P. nephridiatum* cells of the population HEa3 was well visible under DIC microscopy (Fig. 1A–C). Infected nucleus was always slightly larger in size than the aposymbiotic one. The Ma infection was mainly constituted by rod-shaped bacteria of two morphological forms: small reproductive form (RF), 2.0–3.0 \times 0.7–0.9 μm , and relatively big infectious form (IF), 4.5–14.0 \times 0.7–0.9 μm , randomly distributed in the karyoplasm. In cases of hyperinfection, the Ma was distinctly larger than aposymbiotic one and full of IFs (Fig. 1C).

The RFs had typical homogenous prokaryotic cytoplasm (Fig. 2A; 3D; 4A). The IFs consisted of longer straight bacteria with differentiation into cytoplasmic and periplasmic parts and a recognition tip-like structure (Fig. 2A, B; 3D; 4A). The periplasmic part of IFs manifested further subsections with different density of deposited material. At least two different periplasmic regions could be discriminated on the bases of their density: darker, electron-dense part and a lighter one (Fig. 2B; 3D). The IF's cytoplasm was more heterogeneous and denser than the RF's cytoplasm (Fig. 2A; 3D). The majority of IFs inside the Ma manifested the cell' membrane surrounded by fine fibrous material and, in some cases (especially close to the nuclear envelope), possessed an additional membrane covering this fibrous-like layer (Fig. 4A, B). Some intermedial forms reached 5–10 μm in length but they did not show yet the cell compartmentalization typical of the IFs. During cell division of infected ciliates, we never observed the so called “connecting piece”, an equatorial part of the dividing host nucleus where the majority of IFs are gathered, which is a characteristic trait for the majority of *Holospora* species (i.e., *H. obtusa*, *H. elegans*, *H. undulata*, *H. curviuscula*, and *H. acuminata*). Both forms of bacteria segregated among the daughter Ma quite randomly (Fig. 3E, F).

Some of IFs with additional membrane surrounding the fine fibrous-like layer were detected either nearby the nuclear envelope or in the cytoplasm (Fig. 4). We performed ultrastructural observations to demonstrate the interactions between IFs and nuclear membranes for *P. putrinum* and *P. nephridiatum* symbionts. In both cases, the HLB' release process from the nucleus was the reverse of the infection process (Fokin & Sabaneyeva, 1997), with bacteria sluicing through the intermembrane space of the nuclear envelope (Fig. 4A, B). This process involved firstly the formation of a fine fibrous layer around the IF and then an external membrane was appearing, which further fusion with the nuclear envelope caused the bacteria “locking” into the

Fig. 1. A-E. Morphology of “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*” infecting the macronucleus of *Paramecium nephridiatum* EHa3. (A) General view of infected ciliate, double-arrow indicates the infected macronucleus (Ma). (B) The part of infected Ma under higher magnification. (C) Part of crushed infected Ma, both reproductive (arrowhead) and infectious forms (arrow) of the bacterium are visible. (D) Central part of dividing infected Ma, no connecting piece is present. (E) Infected host cell just after division. (A-C) Living observation at DIC. (D, E) FISH with eubacterial probe (D) and alphaproteobacterial probe (E). Scale bars 25 μm (A), 15 μm (B, E), 10 μm (C) and 12 μm (D).

cytoplasm of the host cell (Fig. 4A-C). This process was already described in detail by previous studies (Fokin & Sabaneyeva, 1997; Fokin, 2015.) Structure of the fibrous layer is well visible on tangential sections (Fig. 4B).

Morphological comparison between the newly detected HLB of *P. nephridiatum* and the previously described Ma symbiont of *P. putrinum* (Fokin et al., 1996) revealed great

similarity between them (Fig. 2A; 4B). The IFs of the HLB in *P. putrinum* measured $5.0\text{--}17.0 \times 0.7\text{--}0.9 \mu\text{m}$ with both relatively rounded ends; the RFs measured $1.5\text{--}2.5 \times 0.6\text{--}0.7 \mu\text{m}$.

During division of the infected Ma, the HLB of *P. putrinum* did not produce the connecting piece as well (Fig. 3E, F). The daughter cells always inherited both bacterial forms

Fig. 2. A, B. Transmission electron micrographs (TEM) of “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*” from *Paramecium nephridiatum* EHa3. (A) Part of the infected macronucleus (Ma), transversal, and longitudinal sections of infectious bacterial forms (IF), and transversal sections of reproductive forms (RF) are present; in the IF sections both cytoplasmic (Cp) and periplasmic bacterial zone (P) are visible. (B) Apical end of the IF with Cp, P, and recognition tip (arrow). The periplasmic part manifests subdivision into several zones according to the density of deposited material. Scale bars 0.6 μm (A) and 0.5 μm (B).

in their Ma. However, some IFs often were detected in the cytoplasm at different stages of the host life cycle, possibly after releasing from the infected nucleus (Fig. 3A, B). The same was observed for EHa3 cells.

Thus, in both cases bacteria had a typical HLB life cycle with IF and RF forms, and had no ability to induce a connecting piece. Sometimes, the infected Ma could be overpopulated by hundreds of bacteria and

become distinctively larger in size than uninfected nucleus (Fig. 3A).

The obtained 16S rDNA sequence of the symbionts of EHa3 population (1,432 bp, accession number: OQ550417) resulted 99.77% identical with the one of “*Ca. Gortzia yakutica*” YA111-52, from *P. putrinum* (MT421880) (Belyavskaja et al., 2020) and the two sequences clustered together in the phylogenetic analysis

Fig. 3. A–F. Macronuclear symbiont of *Paramecium putrinum* PpKH1-1, possibly identified as “*Candidatus Gortzia yakutica*”. (A, E) Phase contrast; (B) Bright field; (F) DIC. (A) Living cell showing a hyperinfected macronucleus (Ma) and an infectious form (IF) in the food vacuole (double arrowheads). (B) Infected cell after Feulgen staining; some IFs (arrows) in the cytoplasm. Micronucleus (Mi). (C) Infected cell after FISH with eubacterial probe, arrowheads indicate food vacuoles. (D) Transmission electron microscopy image of longitudinal sections of reproductive forms (RF) and IF, with cytoplasmic part (Cp), periplasmic part (P), and recognition tip (double arrowhead) well visible. (E) Division of infected living cell of *P. putrinum*. (F) Closer view of the dividing infected Ma without connecting piece, living cell. Scale bars 15 μm (A, B), 10 μm (C, F), 1.0 μm (D) and 20 μm (E).

with high statistical support (100/1.00) (Fig. 5). Thus, we conclude that EH3 HLB also belonged to “*Ca. G. yakutica*” and, accordingly to our observations, we are pretty sure that the same concerns the HLB from *P. putrinum* described in 1996 (Fokin et al., 1996).

HLB of *Paramecium polycaryum* EgA-21 – *Preeria caryophila*

Infection of the Ma in the cells belonging to the strain EgA-21 was well visible under DIC microscopy (Fig. 6). Infected nucleus was always slightly larger in size than the aposymbiotic one. Cases of hyperinfection were not detected (Fig. 6A, B, E, F) in natural conditions. The Ma infection was mainly represented by rod shaped bacteria of two morphological forms, small RFs, $1.5\text{--}2.5 \times 0.5\text{--}0.7$

μm , straight (sometimes almost coccoid or more elongated), curved or even crescent-shaped, and relatively long IFs, $4.0\text{--}7.0 \times 0.3\text{--}0.35$ μm , straight or more commonly spiral-shaped, with tapered ends and sub-compartmentalization into cytoplasmic, periplasmic and recognition tip regions (Fig. 7). Nevertheless, some RFs could reach $3.5\text{--}5.0$ μm in length, but still did not manifest the typical IF structure. Bacteria were quite randomly distributed in the nucleus.

The periplasm of the IF was always subdivided into two rather homogenous parts but with different density and, sometimes, a sort of “membrane cluster”, which topologically separated the periplasm from the cytoplasm, was detected (Fig. 7B). It had another structure resembling a cluster of closely attached membranes, sometimes with a single dark inclusion (Fig. 7A, B). The longest IFs simulta-

Fig. 4. A-C. Transmission electron micrographs of macronuclear symbionts of *Paramecium putrinum* PpKH1-1, possibly identified as “*Candidatus* Gortzia yakutica”. (A, B) Infectious form (IF) communicating with the nuclear envelope: fusion between membrane surrounding the bacterium (arrowhead) and the inner nuclear membrane (arrow), fine fibrous layer well visible (asterisk). (C) IF in the cytoplasm nearby the macronucleus inside a membrane vesicle (double arrowhead). Scale bars 0.2 μm (A, B) and 0.3 μm (C).

neously manifest periplasmic parts and recognition tips in both ends of cell and, probably, could divide in such condition (Fig. 7A, B).

Furthermore, we used for comparison some of own TEM pictures made for *P. biaurelia* infected with *Pr. caryophila* (Figs. 8–10). They revealed several morphological peculiarities of the IFs. Very often IFs of those bacteria also manifested recognition tip and periplasmic structures at both ends of the cell. We could distinguish at least two different periplasmic regions on the bases of their density: a darker, electron-dense part and a lighter one. Moreover, cytoplasm and periplasm were divided by the inner membrane forming several convolute layers, a sort of “membrane cluster” (Fig. 8B), which continued along cytoplasmic part of cell as a single membrane layer. The latter was located between the cytoplasmic volume of the bacterium and its envelope (Fig. 8B). The sizes of the bacteria from *P. biaurelia* were $4.5\text{--}8.0 \times 0.3\text{--}0.35 \mu\text{m}$ for IF and $1.5\text{--}3.0 \times 0.35\text{--}0.4 \mu\text{m}$ for RF. Thus, the size and ultrastructure of the HLB’ IFs in *P. polycaryum* and IFs of *Pr. caryophila* from *P. biaurelia* were quite similar. Also sizes of RFs from *P. polycaryum* are comparable to those from *P. biaurelia*. As last remark, we should stress that the diameter of RFs was usually a

bit larger compared to the diameter of IFs in *Pr. caryophila*, generally.

However, ultrastructure of IFs of *Pr. caryophila* ready to be released from the infected nucleus in *P. biaurelia* had some more specific features. In *Pr. caryophila* IFs can be released from the infected Ma by probably different ways compared to the ones of HLB and “*Ca. Holospora parva*” (reverse of the infection process) or of “classical” *Holospora* (via the connecting piece). This process could involve the release of part of the infected karyoplasm, containing clusters of IFs, into the cytoplasm (Fig. 9D; 10B, C). At first, the IFs need to generate on their surface some sort of fine additional layer, which does not look identical with fine fibrous decoration of IFs in other HLB. Probably, as the next step, a bacterium is surrounded by additional fibrous layer and membrane; finally, those layers are replaced by some sort of small vesicle stripes (Fig. 9A-C) nearby nuclear envelope. In some cases, before releasing several IFs were found separated by a common membrane in the infected Ma (Fig. 10D). Thus, IFs of *Pr. caryophila* could be released to the cytoplasm either individually or in groups (Fig. 9A, D, E; 10B-D).

The obtained 16S rDNA sequence of HLB from EgA-21 strain (1,485 bp, accession number: OQ550418)

Fig 5. Phylogenetic tree of the family *Holosporaceae* based on 16S rDNA sequences. Numbers associated to nodes represent bootstrap value from maximum likelihood (ML) and posterior probability from Bayesian inference (BI) analyses, respectively (only values of ML > 70% and BI > 0.80 are shown). Particularly, phylogenetic positions of "*Candidatus* *Gortzia yakutica*" from *Paramecium nephridiatum* EHa3 and *Preeria caryophila* from *P. polycaryum* EgA-21 are shown. Sequences obtained in the present work are in bold.

resulted 99.93% identical with the one of *Pr. caryophila* strain GFg (LT616953) from *P. octaurelia* (Potekhin et al., 2018). In general, this sequence showed identity values with other *Pr. caryophila* sequences not lower than 99.18%, and the phylogenetic analysis showed that they clustered together with high statistical support (100/1.00) (Fig. 5). Therefore, we are confident to conclude that *P. polycaryum* strain EgA-21 in fact was infected by *Pr. caryophila*.

***Holospora undulata* from *Paramecium caudatum* PcSK12**

The TEM picture newly obtained for *H. undulata* from *P. caudatum* PcSK12 showed recognition tip, cytoplasmic and periplasmic part of IF (Fig. 11A) and the connecting piece, in which some microtubule-like structures were linking IFs (Fig. 11B). These pictures are presented in this work mainly for comparative purpose, to facilitate the reader to compare

Fig. 6. A-F. *Preeria caryophila* from *Paramecium polycaryum* EgA-21. (A-D) Living cell observed at DIC. (A) General view of the infected ciliate. (B) Part of infected macronucleus (Ma). (C) Crushed infected Ma, both bacteria forms: infectious form (IF – arrows) and reproductive form (RF – arrowheads) are visible. (D) One of IFs manifests double length (asterisk). (E, F) FISH of the same infected cell with two probes: eubacterial (E) and alphaproteobacterial (F). Scale bars 12 μm (A), 7 μm (B-D) and 14 μm (E, F).

inner structures among holosporas and HLB (see Discussion section).

Experimental infections

For “*Ca. G. yakutica*” the symbionts’ maintenance seemed to be not very stable, and infection was not easy to achieve experimentally. Subcloning of the native population did not yield results: infected cells could not divide more than twice and then died. Attempts to

obtain experimental infection of both aposymbiotic *P. nephridiatum* and *P. woodruffi* using hyperinfected cell of the strain EHa3 via co-cultivation or by adding a droplet with a crashed infected ciliate did not give a positive result. At the same time, in the infected original population itself, a “balance” was maintained between non-infected, infected and hyperinfected cells. Infection in the original *P. nephridiatum* population EHa3 was maintained for four months, and then was no longer detected.

Fig. 7. A-D. Transmission electron micrographs of *Preeria caryophila* inside the infected macronucleus of *Paramecium polycaryum* EgA-21. (A) Part of the macronucleus with both infectious form (IF) and reproductive form (RF); some of IFs manifested two periplasmic compartments (P) in both ends of the bacterium; between them and the cytoplasmic part (Cp) some “membrane clusters” (closely related membranes) are visible (arrows). (B) IF with double periplasmic zone at both ends of bacterium and, recognition tip (double arrowheads) at higher magnification. (C) Part of infected macronucleus (Ma) and one native micronucleus (Mi); one infectious form (IF), in the cytoplasm, cross section (asterisk). (D) Part of IF, longitudinal section; it manifested cytoplasmic (Cp), two periplasmic (P) zones with different density and the recognition tip (double arrowheads). Scale bars 0.4 μm (A-C) and 0.1 μm (D).

Infection of *P. polycaryum* strain EgA-21 HLB with *Pr. caryophila* appeared to be stable (the infection is currently maintained for more than two years), that allowed to investigate infectious capacity for the HLB. Experimental infection was performed successfully for all 14 recipient stocks of *P. polycaryum* isolated from eight different locations from Iceland to Egypt and from France to India. Instead, experimental infections of *P. aurelia* spp. and *P. caudatum* strains using homogenate method had no success. However, co-cultivation attempts resulted in the infection of two aposymbiotic strains of the *P. aurelia* complex, one of which represented *P. biaurelia*.

Discussion

HLB host specificity paradigm

Symbiosis in ciliates shows a variety of combinations between the hosts and HLB representatives. The complex life cycle of infectious HLB and their nuclear and host specificity suggest that there is a system of diverse interactions with the host, both at the stage of infection and during the maintenance of bacteria in the nuclei (Fokin, 1993, 1998, 2004; Görtz, 1996; Fokin and Görtz, 2009). Moreover, most

stages of infection appear to be under the double control of the symbiont and the host (Fokin and Skovorodkin, 1991a, b; Fokin, 1998; Fokin et al., 2003a, b). However, all hosts usually live perfectly without such symbionts and, quite probably, all HLB should be treated as parasites of ciliates (Fokin and Görtz, 2009), even if it has been demonstrated that the presence of *H. undulata* can confer a certain resistance to its host against environmental stressors, such as salinity and temperature (Fujishima et al., 2023), at the expense of a reduced mobility (Zilio et al., 2023).

The presence of the same symbionts in different host species can usually involve phylogenetically close hosts, which has long been known from general parasitology and is fully confirmed by studies on ciliates (Smurov and Fokin, 1995; Hori and Fujishima, 2003; Fokin, 2000). Nevertheless, there are some exceptions. For example, the presence of methanogenic bacteria, widely represented in protists living in anoxic condition, rather speaks of the ecological unity of these unicellular organisms (Fenchel and Finlay, 1991; Shinzato et al., 2018; Nitla et al., 2019). The same can be addressed to sulphate-reducing or thiotrophic ectosymbiotic bacteria from anaerobic ciliates (Fenchel and Ramsing, 1992; Bright et al., 2014, 2019). The formation of a common

Fig. 8. A, B. Transmission electron micrographs of *Paramecium biaurelia* PnMS212 cells infected with *Preeria caryophila*. (A) Part of infected macronucleus (Ma) and part of the native micronucleus (Mi), visible on the right upper corner; both infectious form (IF) and reproductive form (RF) are present; some of IFs manifested “membrane clusters” (closely related membranes) in the border between periplasmic and cytoplasmic compartments (arrows); the longest IF has two periplasmic regions at both ends of bacterium; one IF is in the cytoplasm (asterisk). (B) IF with double periplasmic zone at both ends of bacterium at higher magnification; distinctive “membrane clusters” (arrow) at the border between periplasm and cytoplasm of the bacterium well visible. Scale bars 0.3 μm .

cell organization, e.g. the evolutionary transformation of mitochondria into hydrogenosomes in these protists (Biagini et al., 1997; Müller, 2012) was accompanied by the appearance of mutualistic symbiosis with methanogens that utilize hydrogen.

The present finding of two HLB in new hosts, i.e. “*Ca. G. yakutica*” in *P. nephridiatum* and *Pr. caryophila* in *P. polycaryum*, encouraged us to reconsider the host-

specificity of *Holospora* and HLB and formulate some further considerations.

Analysis of the available literature and own materials have shown that the host species specificity, treated as a strict feature of HLB in the 1970–1980 s, is far to be the paradigm for these symbioses. Not by chance, it was observed in the infection experiments that the *Holospora*-like symbiont from *P. putrinum* could infect the Ma of

Fig. 9. A-E. Transmission electron micrographs of *Paramecium biaurelia* PnMS212 cells infected with *Preeria caryophila*. (A) Infectious forms (IF) ready to be released into the cytoplasm; two bacteria, located under the nuclear envelope, show very peculiar concentric layers formed by small vesicles (arrowheads). (B) Part of the infected macronucleus; some IFs manifested particular fibrous decoration (double arrowheads). (C) Fibrous complex around of IF under higher magnification. (D) Several IFs with small volume of karyoplasm covered by joint membrane in the cytoplasm. (E) Couple of IFs in the cytoplasm decorated by single membrane each (double arrows). Scale bars 0.3 μm (A, B), 0.2 μm (C) and 0.35 μm (D, E).

P. polycaryum and could be maintained for some time also in *P. duboscqui* (Fokin et al., 1999; Fokin, 2000). “*Holospora bacillata*” from *P. nephridiatum* could infect also the Ma of *P. woodruffi*, *P. duboscqui* and *P. calkinsi*. In the latter case the bacterium was also maintained during several weeks in the experimentally infected lines. Moreover, the stable presence of “*H. bacillata*” in the native population of *P. calkinsi* was found at the brackish pool at the White Sea coast, and the isolate from that population was able to infect and persist in both *P. calkinsi* and *P. nephridiatum* present in that biotope (Fokin and Sabaneyeva, 1993; Fokin and Sabaneyeva, 1990). Apparently, this species does not make distinction between closely related host ciliates. Similar examples are known for some other associations between HLB and ciliates investigated under laboratory conditions (Barhey and Gibson, 1984; Fujishima and Fujita, 1985; Fokin, 1993, 2004, 2012; Boscaro et al., 2013; Serra et al., 2016).

This phenomenon of HLB promiscuity was investigated in detail for symbioses between *Pr. caryophila* and several species of the *P. aurelia* complex (*P. biaurelia*, *P. tetaure-*

lia, *P. octaurelia*, *P. novaurelia*) as well as *P. jenningsi*, *P. caudatum* and even *P. multimicronucleatum*, and *P. putrinum* (Potekhin et al., 2018). The list of the potential hosts determined in that work could be incomplete, as selection of strains of all tested *Paramecium* species was limited, and all negative results of experimental infections may be due to particular incompatibility between host and symbiont genotypes (Bella et al. 2016). However, each positive result is meaningful as it confirms that bacteria can survive in the certain host species. In the present work we describe *P. polycaryum* as a natural host of *Pr. caryophila*; in previous research this species has not been listed among the hosts (Potekhin et al. 2018). The native infection of *P. caudatum* with *Pr. caryophila*, however, was known much before (Görtz, 1986; Fokin, 1993). The HLB “*Ca. G. infectiva*” was also originally detected in two species, namely *P. jenningsi* and *P. quadecaurelia* (Boscaro et al., 2013). The entrance of this HLB into the target nucleus under experimental infection was also recorded for *P. schewiakoffi*, *P. sonneborni* and even the less closely related *P. caudatum*, but only in *P. jenningsi*

Fig. 10. A-D. Transmission electron micrographs of *Paramecium biaurelia* PnMS212 cells infected with *Preeria caryophila*. (A) Infectious form (IF) in the cytoplasm, probably directed towards the macronucleus; recognition tip (double arrowheads) well visible. (B) Two IFs inside of the same cytoplasmic vacuole. (C) Several IFs inside of autophagic vacuole. (D) A number of infectious forms (IF) isolated inside of macronuclear karyoplasm by a general membrane (arrows) as a big cluster. Few reproductive forms (RF) are visible. Scale bars 0.35 μm .

“*Ca. G. infectiva*” could complete its life cycle (Boscaro et al., 2013).

Thus, while the postulate on strict host specificity still holds for *Holospora*, it appeared to be not true for other HLB such as *Preeria* and “*Ca. Gortzia*”, while there are no data for the fourth HLB genus, the symbiont of *Frontonia* “*Ca. Hafkinia*” (Fokin et al. 2019). Our results of molecular phylogenetic analyses point on coevolution

between *Paramecium* and *Holospora* species. However, *Preeria* and “*Ca. Gortzia*” are scattered among different *Paramecium* species and do not show a clear pattern even for the host preference, not to mention strict specificity. Up to now there is only one species of *Preeria*, and this HLB can infect very distant host species. Three currently known species of “*Ca. Gortzia*”, as already mentioned, were found in different *Paramecium* species, and each of them

Fig. 11. A, B. Transmission electron micrographs of *Paramecium caudatum* PcSK12 infected with the micronuclear bacterium *Holospora undulata*. (A) Infectious form (IF) manifesting “classical” solid periplasmic zone (P) and recognition tip (double arrowheads). (B) Connecting piece full of IFs in the cytoplasm of host cell; many of IFs connected with number of microtubule-like structures (arrows). Cp, cytoplasm. Scale bars 0.5 μm (A) and 1.0 μm (B).

was able to infect several host species. Nothing is known yet about the fine mechanisms of recognition of HLB’ symbionts by *Paramecium*, as well as the molecular crosstalk between *Paramecium* and HLB during infection process. Probably, further discovery of the molecular bases of *Paramecium*-HLB interactions will shed light also on the peculiar details making *Holospora* strictly host-specific, and, at the same time, allowing *Preeria* and “*Ca. Gortzia*” to be promiscuous. However, it is possible to suppose that other HLB are less advanced than the “classical” *Holospora* sp., because a quantitative separation of IFs and RFs with aid of the connecting piece formed during the host nuclear division was never observed. This argues for them being less specialized that may result in also broader host specificity. Indeed, it is generally accepted that the highly evolved parasites are more prone to be strictly host specific (Preer and Preer, 1982).

Insights into *Holospora* and HLB evolution

Until recently the evolution of *Holospora* seemed to be rather untangled, as all known species had similar two-stage lifecycle, and all besides *H. caryophila* showed clear host specificity, so it was assumed that all *Holospora* and HLB were highly specialized and well-adapted symbionts. The majority of holosporas manifested ability to create the

connecting piece during host cell division (Fig. 11B). For couple of decades, this peculiarity served as one of the major diagnostic characters for discrimination of *Holospora* and other HLB species. The present interpretation regarding the formation of the connecting piece in the dividing host nucleus, is that it constitutes a highly derived specialization of the symbiont (Fokin, 2004; Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Lanzoni et al. 2016). Indeed, this ability could be considered an adaptation of bacteria that exploit the host cell division machinery to accomplish own complex life cycle (Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Fokin, 2015) and this peculiar formation is thought to improve the release of the infectious symbionts to the environment (Wiemann and Görtz, 1989; Fokin et al., 1996; Fokin and Sabaneyeva, 1997; Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Fokin, 2015).

However, the lack of the connecting piece was observed for all HLB outside of the *Holospora* genus: in “*Ca. G. infectiva*”, “*Ca. G. shahrazadis*”, “*Ca. G. yakutica*” as well as in *Pr. caryophila* and “*Ca. Hafkinia simulans*” (Boscaro et al., 2013; Serra et al., 2016; Fokin et al., 2019; Fokin and Serra, 2022). It also was not detected in “*H. bacillata*” and “*H. curvata*” (Fokin, 1989; Fokin and Sabaneyeva, 1993). Finally, after description of “*Ca. Holospora parva*” (Lanzoni et al., 2016) which has no ability to form connecting piece but obviously is a representative of the *Holospora* genus, it became clear that such adaptation orig-

inated only at the certain point of *Holospora* evolution and should not be treated as a synapomorphy of the genus. More precisely, the connecting piece was observed in *H. obtusa*, *H. elegans*, *H. undulata*, which form the sister clade of “*Ca. H. parva*”, from a phylogenetic point of view, as well as in *H. acuminata* and *H. curviuscula* that form another monophyletic clade (Fig. 5), (Fokin, 2004; Lanzoni et al., 2016; Fokin et al., 2019). Instead, in many other HLB, and also in “*Ca. G. yakutica*” a fine fibrous-like layer surrounding the IFs is present, probably mediating the escaping process of bacteria from the nucleus to the host cytoplasm.

Moreover, the structure of periplasmic part of IF of “*Ca. H. parva*” reminds that of the “*Ca. Gortzia*” representatives, but not of “classical” holosporas (i.e., *H. obtusa*, *H. elegans*, *H. undulata*, *H. curviuscula*, and *H. acuminata*). Classical characteristics of *Holospora* IFs are the straight rod shape with differentiated cytoplasmic and periplasmic parts and a recognition tip structure (Fig. 11A). In case of “*Ca. H. parva*”, the periplasmic region of the cell always has two different regions, a larger and denser one and another more electronically transparent. The latter characteristic was never recorded in other holosporas but is shared with other HLB. The same characteristics, with some deviation, were observed in both “*Ca. G. yakutica*” and *Pr. caryophila*. In case of “*Ca. G. yakutica*”, its ultrastructure reminds other representatives of the genus, and since a similar ultrastructure had been described also for “*H. bacillata*” and “*H. curvata*”, we can speculate that the two latter species could belong to “*Ca. Gortzia*” but not to *Holospora* genus. Unfortunately, molecular data which could clarify this point are still missing.

Biogeography of *Holospora* and HLB

In the present work we described two HLB retrieved in the new host species: “*Ca. G. yakutica*” in *P. nephridium* from the Baltic Sea coastline, and *Pr. caryophila* in *P. polycaryum* from Egypt.

“*Ca. G. yakutica*” is the only species of the genus retrieved in the northern part of the Boreal hemisphere (Yakutia and the Baltic Sea coastline), since the other two species, “*Ca. G. infectiva*” and “*Ca. G. shahrazadis*”, were detected so far in tropics only, i.e. India and Thailand (Boscaro et al., 2013; Serra et al., 2016). This might suggest that “*Ca. G. yakutica*” is more adapted to cold-temperate climate following the hosts’ distribution. Not by chance *P. putrinum* and *P. nephridium* are mostly found in cold-temperate areas. Although, it cannot be excluded that this suggestion is simply based on the rather few investigations made in tropical areas so far (Serra et al., 2016), as demonstrated by that the finding of *Pr. caryophila* in *P. polycaryum* from Egypt, the first *Preeria* ever found in a tropical country. Indeed, this symbiont was previously retrieved in Europe (mostly in the northern part) and in the USA nearby Boston only, and it was con-

sidered exclusively (and erroneously) adapted to cold-temperate region.

The same concerns *Holospora*, which had been considered an intranuclear symbiont of *P. caudatum* adapted to regions with cold and temperate climate, until *H. obtusa* was found in Araku Hills (Andhra Pradesh, India) and in the south of Honshu Island (Jamaguchi, Japan) (Serra et al., 2016). Recently, *H. elegans* was detected in *P. caudatum* collected nearby Giardino Naxos (Sicily, Italy) (Serra et al., 2016), which can be treated as subtropical areas.

Lastly, in the present work we propose, as has been emphasized before (Fokin and Serra, 2022), to avoid the practice of naming HLB or any other symbiotic bacteria in connection to the geographic region of their finding, adopted by several authors (Korotaev et al., 2020; Beliavskaia et al., 2020), because then it would be quite misleading if the same symbionts are found in other host populations remote from the site of the first isolation. The case of “*Ca. G. yakutica*” described in *P. putrinum* from Yakutia (North-Eastern Siberia, Russia), which, highly likely, has been found long before in Europe (Germany) in the same host, and now reported in *P. nephridium* from the Baltic Sea coast (this study) and from the White Sea coast (E. Sabaneyeva, personal communication), serves as an explicative example. Both host ciliate species are widely distributed around the globe, and we can expect further findings of the same HLB in other regions. It is necessary to stress that in this particular case we observed not only another host and geographical location for the same HLB, but also found it in different ecological conditions, namely fresh and brackish water.

Ultrastructure of *Preeria caryophila*

“Classical” holosporas and other HLB, as known from 1970 s, display a complex life cycle connected to the infection process and are characterized by two different morphotypes (Fig. 11A, B) that serve distinct functions (Ossipov and Ivakhnyuk, 1972; Ossipov and Podlipaev, 1978; Podlipaev and Ossipov, 1979; Görtz, 1983; Fokin, 1993; Fokin and Görtz, 2009; Schrallhammer and Potekhin, 2020). The RFs are typical rod-shaped bacteria ($2.0\text{--}4.0 \times 0.3\text{--}1.5 \mu\text{m}$). They can be found multiplying inside the host nucleus. At some point (usually after one week), probably, after reaching a certain amount, they start to differentiate into IFs. These cells are much longer than RF and can reach, in different HLB, from $5 \text{ to } 30.0 \times 0.3\text{--}3.5 \mu\text{m}$. IF shapes can be straight, spindle-shaped, curved, or sigmoidal. These two stages were well illustrated by TEM for all HLB species, strangely except *Pr. caryophila*. In the first description of this symbiont the author did not present any morphometry for the bacterium, and the only TEM figure was of low resolution (Preer, 1969). Surprisingly, not a single ultrastructural study with good quality images of this bacterium has been done since that publication. One of

the few attempts to investigate the ultrastructure of this HLB was made at a not sufficiently good methodological level (Gibson et al., 1986). The measurements of the IFs size $5.0 \times 0.7\text{--}1.0 \mu\text{m}$ presented in that work were not taken into account further. Also TEM pictures of *Pr. caryophila* published by other authors (Görtz, 1983, 1992; Potekhin et al., 2018) were not clear enough. In all cases, the low magnification of the figures does not allow to say anything about particular structure of the bacterium. Consequently, the size of the RFs and IFs of *Pr. caryophila* was determined only on the basis of light-optical observations. So, usually data presented in the literature on this point are: $1.0\text{--}2.5 \times 0.2\text{--}0.3 \mu\text{m}$ for RFs, $5.0\text{--}6.0 \times 0.2\text{--}0.3 \mu\text{m}$ (Potekhin et al., 2018) or $5\text{--}8 \times 0.2\text{--}0.3 \mu\text{m}$ for IFs (Fokin et al., 1996), and they have never been checked by accurate measuring from the TEM images.

For this reason, the present study is particularly relevant in revealing important details of the ultrastructure of *Pr. caryophila*, useful for comparisons with other HLB. For example, the structure which we described as a “membrane cluster” in IF of *P. caryophila* has never been detected in any other HLB and can be treated as a peculiar characteristic of the *Preeria* genus. IFs of *Pr. caryophila* with a double set of periplasmic structures and two terminal recognition tips are capable of division. As a result, two classical IFs are formed. This feature has so far been noted only for “*H. bacillata*” (Fokin, 1989). The only TEM figure in Preer’s article (Preer, 1969, Fig. 3), even if not so sharp, presents the part with recognition tip and periplasmic zone and seems corresponding to our observations.

TEM imaging of IFs of *Pr. caryophila* ready to be released from the infected nucleus in *P. biaurelia* also provided some new information. In the examined strain IFs, probably, could be released from the infected nucleus by different ways. This process could be either the reverse path of a normal infection, or involved the separation of IFs with some surrounding karyoplasm by a membrane which then fused with the nuclear envelope and symbionts were released into the host cytoplasm, or even involve the direct passage of bacteria through the perinuclear space of the infected nucleus into the cytoplasm (Fig. 4A-C; 9A-C). In any case, such processes were not observed in other HLB, and it looks unique.

Author contributions

Sergei Fokin and Valentina Serra conceived and designed the study. Natalia Lebedeva performed the living observations and the experimental infection experiments. Sergei Fokin performed light and transmission electron microscopy. Valentina Serra, Alexey Potekhin and Leandro Gammuto performed molecular and phylogenetic analysis. Sergei Fokin, Alexey Potekhin, Valentina Serra, and

Leandro Gammuto wrote and revised the paper. Giulio Petroni provided resources and was involved in review and editing. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejop.2023.125998>.

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